

Analyzing Gender Equality At The Modern Olympics Through Pestel And Trend Analysis From Citius, Altius, Fortius to Diversity, Equality, and Inclusivity (Paris 2024)

Modern Olimpiyatlarda Cinsiyet Eşitliğinin PESTEL ve Eğilim Analizi Yoluyla İncelenmesi: Citius, Altius, Fortius'tan Çeşitlilik, Eşitlik ve Kapsayıcılığa (Paris 2024)

Sabiha Gizem Engin¹

*Correspondence:

Sabiha Gizem ENGİN

¹ Yozgat Bozok Üniversitesi, Spor Bilimleri Fakültesi / s.gizemengin@gmail.com, Orcid: 0000-0003-0898-8474

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17158019>

Received / Gönderim: 09.05.2025

Accepted / Kabul: 23.06.2025

Published / Yayın: 30.06.2025

Volume 2, Issue 2, June, 2025

Abstract

The At the inception of the Olympic Games, women's participation was highly limited, with Pierre de Coubertin's negative stance on the role of women in sports laying the foundation for this inequality. However, from the late 20th century onwards, the International Olympic Committee (IOC) adopted policies aimed at increasing the participation of female athletes. The 2024 Paris Olympics marked the pinnacle of these efforts, achieving full gender parity in the number of male and female athletes. This study examines the historical development and current state of gender equality in the modern Olympic Games through the application of PESTEL and trend analysis methodologies. The article analyses the IOC's political, economic, social, technological, and legal strategies to evaluate the impact of its gender equality policies. Furthermore, it highlights the role of media representation, sponsorship, and women's rights movements in this process. The primary aim of the study is to emphasize that gender equality must be achieved not only quantitatively but also qualitatively.

Keywords Gender equality, Olympic Games, IOC policies, Paris 2024, female athletes

Öz

Araştırmanın Olimpiyat Oyunlarının başlangıcında, kadınların katılımı son derece sınırlıydı; Pierre de Coubertin'in kadınların spordaki rolüne yönelik olumsuz tutumu, bu eşitsizliğin temelini oluşturdu. Ancak 20. yüzyılın sonlarından itibaren Uluslararası Olimpiyat Komitesi (IOC), kadın sporcuların katılımını artırmaya yönelik politikalar benimsemiştir. 2024 Paris Olimpiyatları, bu çabaların doruk noktası olmuş ve kadın ve erkek sporcu sayısında tam cinsiyet eşitliği sağlanmıştır. Bu çalışma, modern Olimpiyat Oyunlarında cinsiyet eşitliğinin tarihsel gelişimini ve güncel durumunu PESTEL ve eğilim analizi yöntemleri aracılığıyla incelemektedir. Makalede, IOC'nin cinsiyet eşitliği politikalarının etkisini değerlendirmek amacıyla politik, ekonomik, sosyal, teknolojik ve hukuki stratejileri analiz edilmektedir. Ayrıca bu süreçte medya temsili, sponsorluklar ve kadın hakları hareketlerinin rolü vurgulanmaktadır. Çalışmanın temel amacı, cinsiyet eşitliğinin yalnızca niceliksel değil, niteliksel olarak da sağlanması gerektiğinin altını çizmektir.

Anahtar Kelimeler Cinsiyet eşitliği, Olimpiyat Oyunları, IOC politikaları, Paris 2024, Kadın sporcular

Introduction

Gender equality has become an increasingly important issue in the modern world of sports. The idea that sport should be an inclusive space highlights not only individuals' physical abilities but also its potential to promote social gender equality. In this context, the International Olympic Committee (IOC) has played a significant role in advancing gender equality. However, a historical examination of the IOC reveals that although progress has been made, the process has been rather slow (De Soysa and Zipp, 2019; Donnelly, 2022).

When the IOC was established in 1896 under the vision of Pierre de Coubertin, the founder of the modern Olympic Games, women's participation in sporting events was very limited. Coubertin's negative attitude toward the role of women in sport laid the foundation for gender inequality during the early years of the Olympic Games. However, from the late 20th century onwards, the IOC began to adopt gender equality policies and implemented various reforms to increase women's involvement in sport. Most recently, at the 2024 Paris Games, there was at least an equal number of female and male athletes participating, achieving quantitative "equality."

This study focuses on the Olympic Games, one of the world's most significant international sporting events. Within this context, it examines the historical and conceptual reasons behind the IOC's shift toward gender equality policies. To embrace the Olympics as a fairer and more inclusive mega-event, it is crucial first to achieve numerical equality and then to establish fair competition. Today, from the perspective of event management in sports, gender equality should be regarded not as a privilege specific to certain events but as a fundamental human necessity.

Challenges on Gender Equality in Beginning of Modern Olympics

Pierre de Coubertin, an aristocrat by birth, was the pioneering leader of the philosophy of Olympism and the founder of the Modern Olympic Games. Following initiatives in 1892, the first Modern Olympic Games were held in Athens in 1896. However, the opportunity for women to participate in the early editions of the Modern Olympics was not significantly different from that of the ancient Olympic period. Coubertin, who was raised within the Kassel Christian system, promoted a view that accepted male superiority in environments where men and women coexisted, and therefore was reluctant to allow women's participation in the Games. He believed that gender equality in the Games would challenge male authority. For this reason, he repeatedly expressed on various platforms that women were very delicate and fragile, anticipating future criticism (Memiş and Yıldırım, 2011).

Image 1. Pierre de Coubertin (Olympics.com, 2024)

Coubertin described women's involvement in sports as "against nature" and argued that the Olympic Games should be organized exclusively for male athletes. It can be said that the real reason here is not gender discrimination but the social norms of the period and the prevention of the pleasure and lust that men would feel while watching female athletes. Although this is considered very bigoted and outside the mould of today's modern civilization, such sociological events should be interpreted in accordance with the spirit of the age (Camps Y Wilant & Hirthler, 2025). Regardless of the justification, this attitude resulted in no women competing as athletes in any sport at the 1896 Athens Olympics, marking the beginning of the modern Olympic era.

Image 2. Olympic Games London 1908, Athletics, high jump women (Olympics.com 2025)

At the next Games, the 1900 Paris Olympics, women gained the right to compete in a few sports such as tennis and golf (Chase, 1992). Although this limited participation aligned with the social norms of the time, it remained a symbol of the vast inequality women faced in the world of sports. Over time, women's participation in sporting events increased mainly due to individual efforts and social pressures. This situation highlighted the necessity for the IOC to develop gender equality policies in the following years.

Women Rights Initiatives

Since the mid-20th century, social pressures for greater inclusion of women in sports have steadily increased. Especially during the 1960s and 1970s, the second-wave feminist movement significantly strengthened the idea that women should have equal rights in sports. In response, the International Olympic Committee (IOC) began to take concrete steps to increase women's participation in the Olympic Games during this period (Teetzal, 2006).

In 1979, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women was adopted, marking a major international commitment to gender equality. The International Working Group on Women and Sport (IWG) was established in 1994 to further promote gender equality and empower women and girls in and through sport. At the Fourth World Conference on Women in 1995, the United Nations developed an action plan for equality, development, and peace. In 1996, the IOC decided that at least 10% of the members of international federations and national Olympic committees should be women. This target was raised to 20% by 2005 and, as the numbers increased rapidly, the goal was updated to 30%. In 2014, the IOC and the United Nations agreed on joint actions to support and empower women and girls, launching collaborative projects with UN Women.

Following the 2016 Rio Games, the “One Win Leads to Another” (OWLA) program was implemented in Brazil, using sport as a tool to prevent violence against women and girls. In 2018, the IOC’s Women in Sport and Athletes’ Commission launched the “Gender Equality Review Project,” which produced a comprehensive action plan of 25 recommendations covering participation, portrayal, funding, and governance in sport. In 2020, joint projects with UN Women focused on increasing the number of women in leadership roles, preventing gender-based violence, closing the investment gap in women’s sports, promoting equal economic opportunities, ensuring equal participation in women’s sports, and providing unbiased media coverage and equal opportunities in sport and physical education for girls.

These historical developments demonstrate that the IOC has adopted a comprehensive and long-term approach to gender equality policies. The results of these initiatives are evident in athlete participation: while women accounted for only 2% of Olympic athletes in 1900, this figure rose to 48% at the Tokyo 2020 Olympics. The 2024 Paris Olympics have now achieved full gender parity, underlining the IOC’s ongoing commitment to equality (Donnelly 2025).

Image 3. Participation of female athletes at the Olympic Games (Masterson 2024)

However, the implementation of equality policies has also led to new discussions regarding the gender identities and biological differences of female athletes (Parcina, 2024).

Equality Initiatives (Strategies to Address) on Modern Olympics

The IOC is known to have developed strategies to promote gender equality through collaboration with international organizations such as the UN and UNESCO (Stephens et al., 2021). This cooperation not only increases sport's potential to promote social gender equality but also contributes to creating a more inclusive sports culture.

The steps taken by the IOC to ensure gender equality are reflected in political, legal, economic, social, and technological fields. For example, politically, the IOC holds individual discussions with each country's Olympic committees to promote gender equality. However, the IOC faces challenges in implementing gender equality due to cultural and legal restrictions in some countries. Issues include debates over female participation and sportswear regulations conflicting with local norms. The IOC also collaborates with supranational organizations such as the UN and UNESCO. These partnerships help secure global acceptance of gender equality policies (Stephens et al., 2021). Additionally, policies regarding the participation of LGBTIQ+ individuals and athletes with differences in sex development (DSD) in the Olympics have sparked debates in some countries. Eligibility criteria based on testosterone levels have become a politically sensitive issue (Parcina, 2024).

Economically, investments in female athletes generally remain lower compared to male athletes. The IOC's gender equality policies aim to increase female athletes' access to financial support and sponsorships. As the visibility of female athletes in the Olympics rises, sponsors and media organizations invest more in women's sports. This demonstrates the economic benefits of the IOC's gender equality policies. Furthermore, demands for equal prize money for female and male athletes have contributed to establishing fair regulations.

Social changes encouraging greater female participation in sports support the IOC's policies. However, in some societies, traditional gender roles continue to limit women's involvement in sports. Gender equality is also a key aspect of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), reinforcing the need for progress in this area. Achieving numerical parity in the Olympics is a first step, with further progress expected on transgender and LGBTIQ+ rights. Based on universal human rights laws, the definition of equality and freedom of expression is expanding, framing participation in the Olympics as a human right for transgender athletes. However, national regulations on transgender athletes in the Olympics vary worldwide, creating potential conflicts between IOC guidelines and local laws that may lead to legal challenges (Teetzel, 2006). The legal framework governing transgender athletes' participation differs among countries, and the IOC's standards may conflict with national laws, causing legal debates (Teetzel, 2013).

Equality in Media

The IOC has made significant progress in the field of media within its gender equality project. By reviewing past news, visual content, and media interactions-including texts, audio, and images-deficiencies were identified. Accordingly, the 2021-2024 Media Portrait Guidelines were established. These guidelines clearly outline the points to be considered in news content related to gender equality (IOC 2024b):

- Equal representation of women, men, and mixed teams in all news and visuals,

- Emphasizing athletic performance in images of female athletes without focusing on female body features,
- Avoiding gendered language (e.g., instead of saying “He swam like a man,” use “He swam with determination”),
- Avoiding the use of commonly accepted social roles for women in news texts (such as “She is a mother” or “She is a perfect wife”),
- Ensuring equal representation (not showing only a few athletes from a team but highlighting the entire team),
- In sports news (boxing, gymnastics, etc.), emphasizing qualities like agility, grace, and discipline rather than gender,
- Avoiding negative news content about transgender athletes or those who do not wish to emphasize their gender identity and focusing news on their sporting achievements.

Image 4. Gender-equal, fair and inclusive representation in sport (IOC 2024b)

Alongside these developments, a working group on gender equality was established to address the imbalance among accredited journalists and to provide more opportunities for women (IOC 2024a). At the 2024 Paris Olympic Games, the aim is to increase the proportion of female commentators to nearly 40% by hiring 35 women in the press section. In the Olympic Broadcasting Services (OBS) department, 42 women were employed as broadcast managers, and 13 women staff were hired in the Broadcast Operations Centre at the International Broadcast Centre (IBC), aiming to achieve a 50-50 gender balance. Additionally, 12 former Olympic athletes, most of whom are women, were trained and employed as sports commentators under the “Olympic Commentary Training” project. Another project enabled university students, 57% of whom are women, to participate in the Broadcast Training Programme to work in the press and broadcasting section (IOC 2024c).

Historical Milestones on the Path to Equality

Early Period: 1896-1980 (Limited Participation of Women and First Steps)

At the beginning of the Modern Olympic Games (1896), women’s participation in sporting events was extremely limited. Pierre de Coubertin’s negative attitude toward women’s involvement in sports laid the foundation for gender inequality during this period (Teetzel 2013). Women’s presence in the Olympics began with a small step at the

1900 Paris Olympics, where they competed in a few sports such as tennis and golf (Chase 1992). However, the proportion of female athletes remained below 10% until the mid-20th century.

Middle Period: 1980-2000 (Feminist Movements and Reforms)

From the 1980s onwards, influenced by the second wave of feminism, the idea that women should have equal rights in sports gained strength (Teetzel 2006). Pressure from international organizations (e.g., UNESCO) on gender equality also intensified (Stephens et al., 2021). In response, the IOC began implementing reforms to increase female athlete participation. One of the most important steps was the introduction of quota systems and more inclusive programs to raise women's participation (de Santana, de Oliveira and Uvinha, 2022). As a result, the proportion of female athletes in the Olympics increased rapidly, reaching 34% at the 1996 Atlanta Olympics (IOC Gender Equality Report, 2020).

Contemporary Period: 2000-2025 (Inclusivity and New Debates)

Today, the proportion of female athletes in the Olympics has reached 50%. Moreover, the IOC's gender equality policies have expanded to cover not only equality issues between male and female athletes but also the rights of transgender athletes and athletes with differences in sex development (DSD). Notably, the "Stockholm Consensus" published in 2004 stands out as one of the first official regulations regarding the participation of transgender athletes in the Olympic Games. However, this regulation has been criticized due to the complex relationship between biological sex and gender identity. Eligibility criteria based on testosterone levels have sparked debates about discrimination against female athletes (Lundberg et al., 2024). This issue became particularly prominent in debates concerning South African athlete Caster Semenya's participation in the Olympics.

Advances in media and broadcasting have also supported the increase in the number of female journalists and commentators. Alongside this, there is a shift in the language used in news coverage to downplay gender identity and emphasize sporting achievements.

Image 5. Equality of participation was achieved in Paris 2024 Summer Olympics

Future Period: 2025 and Beyond (Expected Trends)

- New regulations may be introduced to protect the rights of transgender athletes and athletes with differences in sex development (DSD), while also considering biological differences.
- The quantitative equality achieved in athlete numbers may also trigger a transformation in coaching and technical staff. The visual below clearly shows that the number of female coaches is still far from equality.

Image 6. Share of Women Coaches in the Summer Olympics (Kleyn 2023)

An increase in female representation at management levels of sports organizations is anticipated (IOC Gender Equality Report, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

In this study, PESTEL analysis and trend analysis were employed to address the research questions and provide an in-depth evaluation of the subject matter. These two analytical methods were combined with the content analysis approach to systematically evaluate the available literature and data. The methods used in the study are detailed below.

PESTEL Analysis

PESTEL analysis is a strategic analytical tool used to systematically examine the external environment of an organization or sector by evaluating political (P), economic (E), social (S), technological (T), environmental (E), and legal (L) factors (Johnson, Scholes, & Whittington, 2008). In this study, PESTEL analysis was utilized to assess the macro-environmental factors influencing the research topic.

During the analysis process, relevant factors were identified through a literature review, and data collected via content analysis were classified accordingly. Political factors included government policies, regulations, and international relations; economic factors covered market conditions, growth rates, and economic crises; social factors involved demographic changes, cultural trends, and consumer behaviors; technological factors examined technological innovations and digitalization; environmental factors focused on sustainability and environmental policies; and legal factors addressed sectoral regulations and legal frameworks (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

Trend Analysis

Trend analysis is a method used to examine changes over a specific period and predict potential future trends (Makridakis, Wheelwright, & Hyndman, 1998). In this

study, trend analysis was employed to identify current trends related to the research topic and evaluate their potential future impacts.

As part of the trend analysis, data obtained through content analysis were systematically analyzed. The research process involved examining academic articles, reports, and other relevant documents published over a specific timeframe. Trends identified in these documents were categorized using a thematic approach. Particular attention was given to topics such as digitalization, sustainability, and societal transformations. The results of the analysis provided valuable insights into understanding future trends and evaluating their implications for the research topic.

Content Analysis

The data underlying the PESTEL and trend analyses were collected using the content analysis method. Content analysis is a qualitative research technique that enables the systematic examination of written, visual, or auditory materials (Krippendorff, 2004). In this study, relevant literature, sectoral reports, official documents, and media content were reviewed, and the data obtained from these materials were analyzed through thematic coding.

This approach played a crucial role in the collection, organization, and interpretation of data for both PESTEL and trend analyses. The results of the analyses were used to answer the research questions and provide a comprehensive evaluation of the research topic.

The analyses were conducted by examining the development and transformation of the Olympics from past to present, incorporating information from media reports, IOC policies, and the latest developments regarding the Paris 2024 Olympics. The study was conducted between January 15, 2025, and April 30, 2025. Since the study employs the content analysis method, no human subjects were involved, and therefore, obtaining ethical approval was not required.

FINDINGS

IOC Strategies and International Collaborations

The IOC has developed several strategies to enhance gender equality, including:

Participation of Female Athletes

The implementation of quota systems and more inclusive programmes has been aimed at increasing female participation in the Olympics (De Santana, De Oliveira and Uvinha 2022).

Governance and Decision-Making

The IOC promotes female representation at executive levels within sports organisations, encouraging active participation in decision-making processes (Donnelly 2022). Notably, Kirsty Coventry became the first woman elected as the IOC president (BBC 2025).

Education and Awareness

The IOC organises educational programmes to protect female athletes' rights and raise public awareness (Stephens et al. 2021).

Additionally, the IOC collaborates with international organisations such as UNESCO to promote gender equality in sports (Stephens et al. 2021). This collaboration not only

enhances the potential of sports to advance gender equality but also contributes to fostering a more inclusive sports culture.

Table 1. IOC's gender equality policies - PESTEL Analysis

	International Policies and the Role of the IOC	The IOC faces challenges in implementing gender equality due to cultural and legal restrictions in some countries. Issues include debates over female participation and sportswear regulations conflicting with local norms.
Political	UNESCO and UN Collaborations	The IOC collaborates with international organisations such as UNESCO and the United Nations to establish gender equality as a global standard (Stephens et al. 2021).
	LGBTIQ+ and Sex Development (DSD) Policies	LGBTIQ+ and DSD athletes' participation policies have caused controversy. The use of testosterone levels as an eligibility criterion remains a contentious issue (Parcina 2024).
Economic	Resources Allocated to Female Athletes	Investment in female athletes lags behind males. IOC policies aim to increase financial support and sponsorship for women in sports.
	Sponsor and Media Revenues	Growing visibility of female Olympians attracts more investment from sponsors and media, reflecting economic benefits of IOC's equality policies.
	Equal Pay Policies	Calls for equal prize money influence IOC's economic strategies, but full parity across all sports remains unachieved.
Social	Gender Roles	Societal changes support women's sports participation, aligning with IOC policies, though traditional gender roles still limit participation in some communities.
	SDG's and Social Sustainability	Gender equality is now key in SDGs. Olympic numerical parity is a first step, with progress expected on transgender and LGBTIQ+ rights.
Technological	Biological Tests and Data Analysis	Advanced technology enables precise analysis of athletes' biology, but testosterone-based eligibility criteria raise ethical concerns (Lundberg et al. 2024).
	Media and Broadcasting Technologies	Technological advancements have enhanced the visibility of female athletes, further promoting gender equality.
Environmental	Sustainability and Sports	Greater female participation in eco-friendly sporting events can enhance public awareness.
Legal	Equality Laws and Policies	Countries have enacted laws to promote female sports participation, but enforcement impacts the IOC's gender equality policies.
	Human Rights and Transgender Athletes	National regulations on transgender athletes in the Olympics differ globally, creating potential conflicts between IOC guidelines and local laws that may result in legal challenges (Teetzel 2006).

IOC's Gender Equality Policies - Trend Analysis

Participation Trends

Women's participation in the Olympic Games has evolved significantly since their exclusion from the first modern Olympics in 1896. The 1900 Paris Olympics marked the first inclusion of women, albeit in limited events such as golf and tennis. Gradual progress led to the 1928 Games, where women's athletics was introduced. A pivotal moment came in 1991 when the IOC mandated that any new sport added to the Olympic programme must include women's events.

The 2012 London Olympics achieved a milestone with every participating country represented by at least one female athlete. The 2020 Tokyo Olympics saw female participation reach 48%, and the 2024 Paris Olympics finally achieved gender parity in athlete numbers.

Image 7. Share of Women Participants in the Summer Olympics (Statista 2024)

Key factors influencing this progress include women's rights movements, changes in IOC policies, increased media interest, and evolving societal attitudes.

Future trends point towards an increase in mixed-gender events, with 18 different categories including such competitions in the Paris 2024 Olympics.

Demographic Trends

The early Modern Olympic Games were dominated by athletes from Western Europe and North America. However, since the 1970s, participation from developing countries has increased significantly. The 2012 London Olympics marked the first time female athletes from countries like Saudi Arabia, Qatar, and Brunei participated.

Factors contributing to this shift include rising education levels, economic growth, and increased financial support for female athletes' participation.

The future goal is to design an Olympic system ensuring equal and fair participation for female athletes from all countries.

Technological Trends

Initially, Olympic equipment and apparel were designed primarily for men. As female participation increased, sports equipment manufacturers developed gender-specific models. Broadcasting technology has also evolved from terrestrial broadcasting to internet-based streaming services supported by high-resolution cameras and artificial intelligence.

Future trends may include shifts in viewing habits due to AI advancements and the integration of technology in referee decision-making across all sports disciplines.

Social Trends

Society has transitioned from believing that "women cannot participate in sports" to aspiring for full gender equality. Factors contributing to this change include the empowerment of the feminist movement in the 1970s, increased media coverage of female athletes, and the growing presence of women's events in international sports organizations.

In the future, female athletes are expected to gain more prominence in media coverage and recognition for their achievements.

CONCLUSION

From the male-dominated early Modern Olympics to today, significant progress has been made in the IOC's gender equality policies. The participation rate of female athletes in the Olympics increased due to social pressures and feminist movements, and today, gender equality policies have expanded to include the rights of LGBTIQ+ athletes and individuals with biological differences.

On the other hand, the election of a female president (Kirsty Coventry) in March 2025 marks a milestone. These advancements reflect broader societal changes and human rights movements. Progress in media and broadcasting has also supported an increase in the number of female journalists and commentators. Alongside this, there is a shift in news language toward downplaying gender identity and emphasizing sporting achievements.

Today, the IOC plays a more active role in ensuring gender equality. The 2024 Paris Olympics marked a historic milestone. Moving forward, progress on justice rather than mere equality should be prioritized in the IOC's future vision. Although the advances made since Pierre de Coubertin's vision are significant, developing more inclusive and fair policies to eliminate "inequality" remains an imperative. For example, U.S. President Donald Trump's declaration to deny visas for transgender athletes at the 2028 Los Angeles Olympics signals potential future crises. Overcoming these challenges would enable the IOC to serve as a global example not only in the sports world but also in terms of social equality.

All these developments illustrate a historical transformation in which the IOC has shifted from its motto "Citius, Altius, Fortius" to one that prioritizes "Diversity, Equality, and Inclusivity."

Beyanlar / Declarations

Etik Onay ve Katılım Onayı / Ethics approval and consent to participate

Bu çalışmanın hazırlanma ve yazım sürecinde "Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Yönergesi" kapsamında bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuş olup; toplanan veriler üzerinde herhangi bir tahrifat yapılmamış ve bu çalışma herhangi başka bir akademik yayın ortamına değerlendirme için gönderilmemiştir. Makale ile ilgili doğabilecek her türlü ihlallerde sorumluluk yazara aittir

Veri Ve Materyal Erişilebilirliği / Availability of data and material

Bu çalışmanın bulgularını destekleyen veriler, makul talepler üzerine sorumlu yazardan temin edilebilir. Veri seti yalnızca akademik amaçlar için erişilebilir olacak ve verilerin herhangi bir kullanımı, orijinal çalışmayı referans gösterecek ve katılımcıların gizliliğini koruyacaktır.

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The dataset will be accessible only for academic purposes, and any use of the data will recognize the original study and maintain the confidentiality of the participants.

Çıkar Çatışması / Competing interests

Yazarlar, bu makalede sunulan çalışmayı etkileyebilecek herhangi bir çıkar çatışması veya kişisel ilişkiye sahip olmadıklarını beyan etmektedirler.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fon Desteği / Funding

This Bu çalışma, kamu, özel veya kar amacı gütmeyen sektörlerdeki fon sağlayıcı kurumlardan herhangi bir özel destek almamıştır.

This research received no external funding.

Teşekkür / Acknowledgements

None.

APA 7 Citation

Engin, S. G. (2025). Analyzing gender equality at the modern Olympics through PESTEL and trend analysis: From *Citius, Altius, Fortius* to diversity, equality, and inclusivity (Paris 2024). *Journal of Health, Exercise, and Sport Sciences*, 2(2), 51-64. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17158019>
<https://www.ijoss.org/Archive/issue2-volume2/ijoss-Volume2-issue2-06.pdf>

MLA Citation

Engin, Sabiha Gizem. "Analyzing Gender Equality at the Modern Olympics through PESTEL and Trend Analysis: From *Citius, Altius, Fortius* to Diversity, Equality, and Inclusivity (Paris 2024)." *Journal of Health, Exercise, and Sport Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 2, 2025, pp. 51–64. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17158019>.
<https://www.ijoss.org/Archive/issue2-volume2/ijoss-Volume2-issue2-06.pdf>

ISO 690 Citation

ENGİN, Sabiha Gizem. Analyzing gender equality at the modern Olympics through PESTEL and trend analysis: From *Citius, Altius, Fortius* to diversity, equality, and inclusivity (Paris 2024). *Journal of Health, Exercise, and Sport Sciences*, 2025, vol. 2, no. 2, p. 51-64. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17158019>
<https://www.ijoss.org/Archive/issue2-volume2/ijoss-Volume2-issue2-06.pdf>

Vancouver Citation

Engin SG. Analyzing gender equality at the modern Olympics through PESTEL and trend analysis: From *Citius, Altius, Fortius* to diversity, equality, and inclusivity (Paris 2024). *Journal of Health, Exercise, and Sport Sciences* 2025;2(2):51-64. doi:10.5281/zenodo.17158019
<https://www.ijoss.org/Archive/issue2-volume2/ijoss-Volume2-issue2-06.pdf>

References / Kaynaklar

- BBC. (2025). *Olympics* [Online]. Available from: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/sport/olympics/articles/cy4v91e3e1wo> [Accessed 21 March 2025].
- Camps Y Wilant, N., & Hirthler, G. (n.d.). *The rationale behind Coubertin's opposition to women competing in the Olympic Games* [Online]. Available from: <https://www.olympics.com/ioc/pierre-de-coubertin/the-rationale-behind-coubertins-opposition-to-women-competing-in-the-olympic-games> [Accessed 19 April 2025].
- Chase, L. F. (1992). A policy analysis of gender inequality within the Olympic movement. In *Proceedings: First International Symposium for Olympic Research* (pp. 28–39).
- De Santana, W. F., De Oliveira, M. H., & Uvinha, R. R. (2022). Are the Olympics up-to-date? Measures taken by the IOC to enhance gender equality in the Games. *Olimpianos - Journal of Olympic Studies*, 6, 234–250.
- De Soysa, L., & Zipp, S. (2019). Gender equality, sport and the United Nation's system: A historical overview of the slow pace of progress. *Sport in Society*, 22(11), 1783–1800.
- Donnelly, M. K. (2022). *Gender equality and the Olympic programme*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Donnelly, M. K. (2025). *Gender equal Olympics? Events and Society: Bridging Theory and Practice*, 22.
- International Olympic Committee (IOC). (2017a). *Gender equality review project* [Online]. Available from: <https://www.olympics.com/ioc/gender-equality/advocacy-and-support/gender-equality-review-project> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- International Olympic Committee (IOC). (2017b). *Beyond the Games* [Online]. Available from: <https://www.olympics.com/ioc/gender-equality/advocacy-and-support/partnerships> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- International Olympic Committee (IOC). (2020). *Zoom in - Gender equality in the Olympic movement* [Online]. Available from: https://library.olympics.com/default/zoom-femme-et-sport.aspx?_lg=en-GB [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- International Olympic Committee (IOC). (2023). *IOC and UN Women sign new agreement to advance gender equality in and through sport* [Online]. Available from: <https://www.olympics.com/ioc/news/ioc-and-un-women-sign-new-agreement-to-advance-gender-equality-in-and-through-sport> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- International Olympic Committee (IOC). (2024a). *Women in the Olympic movement* [Online]. Available from: <https://stillmed.olympics.com/media/Documents/Olympic-Movement/Factsheets/Women-in-the-Olympic-Movement.pdf> [Accessed 22 April 2025].

- International Olympic Committee (IOC). (2024b). *Portrayal guidelines gender-equal, fair and inclusive* [Online]. Available from: <https://stillmed.olympics.com/media/Documents/Beyond-the-Games/Gender-Equality-inSport/IOC-Portrayal-Guidelines.pdf> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- International Olympic Committee (IOC). (2024c). Olympic broadcasting: More women in key broadcast roles at Paris 2024 [Online]. Available from: <https://www.olympics.com/ioc/news/olympic-broadcasting-more-women-in-key-broadcast-roles-at-paris-2024> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- Johnson, G., Scholes, K., & Whittington, R. (2008). *Exploring Corporate Strategy: Text and Cases*. Pearson Education.
- Kleyn, B. (2023). 'We need women and young girls to see female coaches': The push for gender parity by Brisbane 2032 for both athletes and coaches [Online]. Available from: <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2023-07-31/paris-2024-first-olympics-to-achieve-gender-parity-for-athletes/102644590> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management*. Pearson Education.
- Krippendorff, K. (2004). *Content Analysis: An Introduction to Its Methodology*. Sage Publications.
- Lundberg, T. R., Tucker, R., McGawley, K., Williams, A. G., Millet, G. P., Sandbakk, Ø., & Hilton, E. N. (2024). The International Olympic Committee framework on fairness, inclusion and nondiscrimination on the basis of gender identity and sex variations does not protect fairness for female athletes. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*, 34(3), e14581.
- Makridakis, S., Wheelwright, S. C., & Hyndman, R. J. (1998). *Forecasting Methods and Applications*. Wiley.
- Masterson, V. (2024). How Paris 2024 aims to become the first-ever gender-equal Olympics [Online]. *World Economic Forum*. Available from: <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2024/04/paris-olympics-2024-gender-parity/> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- Memiş, U. A., & Yıldırım, I. (2011). The historical development of women's involvement in sports in western cultures. *Gazi Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 16(3), 17–26.
- Olympics 2024. *Pierre de Coubertin: The colossal legacy of a forgotten hero* [Online]. Available from: <https://www.olympics.com/ioc/news/pierre-de-coubertin-the-colossal-legacy-of-a-forgotten-hero> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- Olympics 2025. *The rationale behind Coubertin's opposition to women competing in the Olympic Games* [Online]. Available from: <https://www.olympics.com/ioc/pierre-de-coubertin/the-rationale-behind-coubertins-opposition-to-women-competing-in-the-olympic-games> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- Parcina, N. (2024). Not a woman enough: An analysis of the representation of female athletes with different sexual development in the IOC policies.
- Statista. (2024). Will the Olympics Finally Reach Gender Equality? [Online]. Available from: <https://www.statista.com/chart/32775/share-of-women-participants-in-the-summer-olympics> [Accessed 22 April 2025].
- Stephens, M., Elsner, P., Matthews, N., & Beadon, G. (2021). Evaluation of the strategic positioning of IOC-UNESCO.
- Teetzel, S. (2006). Equality, equity, and inclusion: Issues in women and transgendered athletes' participation at the Olympics. In *Proceedings: International Symposium for Olympic Research* (pp. 331–339).
- Teetzel, S. (2013). *Rules and reform: Eligibility, gender differences, and the Olympic Games*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- .

Publishers' Note

IJOSS remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.